

Demographic Profile, Epidemiology, Management and Visual Outcomes of Pediatric Cataract in A Tertiary Eye Care Center of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the demographic profile, epidemiology, management, etiology, complications and long-term visual outcome of pediatric cataract surgery at tertiary care center of Bangladesh.

Method: It was prospective study conducted in pediatric Ophthalmology and strabismus department of Ispahani Islamia Eye Institute & Hospital from January - December '2023. The study included 324 cataractous eyes of 204 patients up to 16 years of age who presented to the pediatric outpatient Department. Exclusion criteria were congenital glaucoma, anterior segment dysgenesis, optic nerve pathology with other syndromes disorders. Detailed ophthalmic examinations including visual acuity, fundus examination, retinoscopy, biometry were performed. Irrigation and aspiration of lens matter with CCC, AVT, +/- PPC and +/- IOL implantation was done. Follow up was done at coming morning, first & fourth week followed by three and six months.

Result: Mean age of presentation was 4.2 ± 2.2 years. Male was 55% whereas 45% females. Cataract was in 324 eyes out of 204 children. Bilateral cataract in 58% children while 42% had unilateral involvement. Most common etiology were maternal TORCH infection (39.2%) followed by idiopathic (14.7%), Prematurity (19.6%), birth trauma (11.8%). Post operative complications were posterior capsular opacification (34.3%), Iridocyclitis (19.6%), secondary glaucoma (5.9%), striae keratopathy (27.5%). Visual acuity $<6/18$ Log MAR 0.5 was seen in 62.7% eyes, $6/18 - 6/60$ Log MAR 0.5-1 in 29.4% eyes, $<6/60$ Log MAR 1 in 7.8% eyes.

Conclusion: It is crucial to keep special concern to timely screening and manage such case for better visual future.

KEYWORDS: Pediatric Cataract, Etiology, Complication, Visual Outcome.

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INTRODUCTION

Pediatric cataract is one of the primary causes of preventable childhood blindness, with an estimated global prevalence ranging from 1 to 15 per 10,000 children [1]. The epidemiology of childhood cataract is complicated and it represents a group of etiologies defined by age. Of the 1.4 million blind children globally, an estimated 190,000 (14%) were caused by lens-related conditions. [2] Although the actual number varies from country to country, in Bangladesh, it is estimated that 49,000 children are blind with one third due to congenital cataract. [3] Impairment of vision in the early years of life can adversely affect the overall development of a child with far-reaching personal, educational, occupational, and social effects. [4] Consequently, early detection and treatment are crucial for maximizing visual development and preventing amblyopia. [5] Treatment of congenital or developmental cataract poses a challenge to ophthalmologists, patients, and parents in terms of visual outcomes and rehabilitation. [6] Timely intervention and optical rehabilitation in a congenital cataract is crucial for long-term visual development.

Its prevalence is 3 to 4 per 10,000 children in Europe [2]. There are 200,000 children around the world and 133,000 in developing countries that suffer from blindness due to congenital cataract [3]. In general, the prevalence of congenital cataract as the most

Demographic Profile, Epidemiology, Management and Visual Outcomes of Pediatric Cataract in A Tertiary Eye Care Center of Bangladesh

common preventable cause of blindness in childhood has been reported from 1 to 15 per 10,000 children, while it is from 1 to 3 per 10,000 births in developing countries [4,5]. Cataracts in children are mostly congenital as well as acquired cataracts (e.g. ocular trauma). [6,7]. Etiology of congenital or acquired childhood cataract includes ocular abnormalities, ocular trauma, intrauterine infections, associated syndromes, or hereditary causes [8]. The World Health Organization's (WHO) initiative for the global elimination of blindness has targeted avoidable causes and has given utmost priority to childhood blindness [9]. It is extremely necessary to identify and manage cataracts in children because they can lead to tremendous economic, emotional and social burdens to the family, child, and society. International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research 670 screening in OPDs, whereas some are diagnosed after parents noticed strabismus or leukocoria [10]. Outcomes of pediatric cataract vary with time as a child grows and develops, unlike that of an adult.

Fig: Congenital cataract

The results of this study will be of clinical significance to pediatric cataract management, considering the surgical timing, approach and control of complications, to achieve an ideal visual outcome.

MATERIAL & METHODS

The present study was a prospective study which was conducted in the Department of pediatric Ophthalmology and strabismus of Ispahani Islamia Eye Institute & Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. during period from January 2023 to December 2023 and followed up for consecutive 1 years. The study included 324 cataractous eyes of 204 pediatric patients up to 16 years of age who presented to the pediatric outpatient Department. Exclusion criteria were infection, congenital glaucoma, anterior segment dysgenesis, optic nerve or other fundus abnormalities, prematurity and cataract associated with other syndromes and systemic disorders. was noted. A detailed history of ante-natal period including any maternal drug intake, maternal fever with rash, radiation exposure per-natal and post-natal period, was taken. After reviewing the history, ophthalmic examinations including visual acuity, fundus examination, retinoscopy, keratometry, and B-scan ultrasonography were performed. Relevant laboratory investigations for anesthesia fitness for surgery, TORCH and to rule out any metabolic diseases were undertaken. Visual acuity was assessed according to the age and performance of the patient (e.g., preferential-looking charts at ages up to 6 months, Cardiff charts at ages up to 2 years, KP charts at ages up to 4 years, or Snellen acuity thereafter) and was presented in Snellen acuity notation. The type, size, density and morphology of cataract were noted using diffuse, focal and retro illumination. Intra-ocular pressure was measured using Goldmann Applanation tonometer or I-care hand held tonometer, depending upon the age of the child if necessary. Fundus examination was done with indirect ophthalmoscope. In cases, wherever fundus evaluation was not possible due to dense and total. cataract, a B-Scan ultrasound examination was performed to rule out any posterior segment pathology. Corneal curvature was measured using keratometer. IOL power calculation was done using SRK II and Hoffer-Q formulae. Under correction of IOL power was done according to the Ashok Gurg formula. Dilatation of pupil was done using cyclopentolate 1% and phenylephrine 2.5% at 90, 60, 30 and 15 minutes pre-operatively. In all cases, irrigation and aspiration of lens matter with Bimanual irrigation aspiration or phaco aspiration was done combined with wide anterior capsulotomy. Implantation of IOL was done after the age of 2 year following irrigation and aspiration of lens matter. Primary posterior capsulotomy was done for the cases up to 5 years of age and having nystagmus. In children with bilateral cataract, eye with poorer vision was operated first and surgery for second eye was done after seven days. The IOL power was determined by A scan Biometry or pre-operatively using SRK-II formula in cooperative children where keratometry was possible.

Fig: Bilateral pediatric cataract

Fig: Unilateral pediatric cataract

The IOL power reduction was

- a) 2–4-year age -15%
- b) 4–8-year age -10%
- c) >8 year – Full emmetropic correction

A detailed pre-anesthetic checkup was done by qualified anesthesiologist. All the surgeries were done by highly qualified pediatric ophthalmologist under General Anesthesia (GA). Informed written consent was obtained for all patients from parent or guardian after discussion of risk, benefit and post operative care.

The standard pediatric cataract surgery followed:

- a) Lens aspiration + Primary posterior capsulotomy (PPC)+Anterior Vitrectomy (AV) <2 years old
- b) Lens aspiration+ Primary Posterior Capsulotomy (PPC)+AV+IOL implantation >2-8 years old
- c) Lens Aspiration +IOL implantation>5-year-old

Postoperatively antibiotic, steroid drop, mydriatic agent, systemic antibiotic and painkiller was started. All the children were kept on topical drops for four weeks. All the children were evaluated at first, fourth week followed by every month for next three months and then every six months for 1 year. During the follow-up any post-operative complications were noted and refraction was done. Amblyopia was corrected using occlusion therapy in unilateral cases.

On the final follow-up visit after 1 year, all patients' best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA), compliance, follow-up frequency, and complications were noted. Visual acuity was assessed using the preferential looking paradigm, Teller Acuity Cards, or Kay pictures, depending on the age of the subjects. Each eye was tested with the other eye occluded and acuity measures recorded were then transposed to Snellen notation. Refraction was done in all eyes.

Demographic Profile, Epidemiology, Management and Visual Outcomes of Pediatric Cataract in A Tertiary Eye Care Center of Bangladesh

RESULTS

A total of 324 cataractous eyes of 204 pediatric patients were enrolled in the present study. Mean age of children was 4.2 ± 2.2 years. Among all cases, cataract was seen in 324 eyes. Out of 204 children, 55% were males and 45% cases were females. Bilateral cataract eyes were seen in 58% children and 42% had unilateral involvement.

Demographical Characteristic & epidemiological finding of congenital cataract

Characteristic	Number	Percentage
Mean Age of presentation (At the time of 1 st visit)	4.2+/-2.2 year	
Gender		
Male	112	55%
Female	92	45%
Laterality		
Unilateral	84	42%
Bilateral	120	58%
Type of cataract		
Cortical	124	38%
Nuclear	68	21%
Traumatic	44	13.5%
Membranous	52	16 %
PSC / Posterior	36	11.5%
lenticonus		
Hailing Area		
Urban	84	41%
Rural	120	59%
Family History	64	31.4%
Socioeconomic condition		
Poor	120	59%
Middle Class	70	34.3%
Upper class	14	6.7%
H/O Consanguinity	48	23.5%

Etiology of congenital cataract

Cause	Number	Percentage
Idiopathic	30	14.7%
TORCH infection	80	39.2%
Prematurity	40	19.6%
Metabolic cause	8	3.9%
Drug exposure	16	7.8%
Birth trauma	24	11.8%
Others	06	2.9%

Post operative complication in follow up visit

Complication	Number	Percentage
Posterior Capsular opacity	70	34.3%
Shallow AC	12	5.9%
Post operative striae keratopathy	56	27.5%
Hyphema	6	3%
Secondary Glaucoma	12	5.9%
Iridocyclitis	40	19.6%
Retained Lens matter	4	1.9%
Pupil capture IOL	4	1.9%

Post operative final visual acuity

Final Visual Acuity	Number	Percentage
< 6/18 log MAR 0.5	128	62.7%
6/18 -6/60 log MAR0.5-1	60	29.4%
< 6/60 Log MAR 1	16	7.8%

DISCUSSION:

Cataract surgery in the pediatric age group is challenging. The challenges include preoperative evaluation, intraoperative surgical difficulties, and postoperative visual rehabilitation. These challenges, especially, the preoperative assessment and postoperative care, are further doubled while dealing with patients with systemic comorbidities [13]. Childhood cataracts are mostly congenital, but cataract can also develop following trauma, which are mostly unilateral [6]. Other etiological factors for childhood cataracts, congenital or acquired, includes hereditary causes, intrauterine causes, systemic syndromes, ocular abnormalities, maternal drug intake, [8]. There are various factors that determine the outcome of pediatric cataract surgery. include age at presentation, age at the time of surgery and associated ocular abnormalities. Early detection and rapid referral are most important factors for evaluating surgical indications for successful management of pediatric cataract [14]. In the present study, a total of 324 cataractous eyes of 204 pediatric patients’ eyes were enrolled. Most of the cases 34(34%) were in age group of 6-8 years. Mean age was 4.2+/-2.2 years. Most of the children presented late to the hospital with regards to age of the child. The late presentation to the hospital for surgery has a significant impact on the normal development of binocular single vision. Similar results have been reported by Ghodke A et al, with a mean age of 5.08 years at the time of surgery [15]. Study from Rawanda has reported mean age of 6.6 years [16] and a study from Nepal reported mean age of 7 years [17]. Late presentation to the hospital for pediatric cataract surgery is common in developing countries due to lack of access to good medical facilities and low level of education among the parents. In the present study cataract was greatly seen in male children 112(55%) as compared to female 92(45%). Some studies [18,19] reported one reason is that in a lot of African communities, boys are awarded a higher societal value than girls. Other studies on pediatric cataract surgery from Africa have reported the similar findings of gender discrepancy with similar explanations [20,21]. A study done by Gogate et al included significantly more males (18) than females (8) [22]. They attributed the reason to less access to eye care facilities for females in India. A study conducted in Nepal by Chaudhary Set an in 2017 found male: female ratio of 1.3:1, 57% were males [18]. In the present study, there were 84 (42%) cases of unilateral and 120 (58%) cases of bilateral cataract. Khandekar R et al reported that bilateral cataract was six times more common than unilateral cataract [23]. Ramteke P et al in their study reported that 57.30% patients had unilateral and 42.69% patients had bilateral cataract [24]. A study published in 2012, conducted in blind schools in Andhra Pradesh shows whole globe anomalies to be the main cause of blindness [25]. A population-based study conducted

Demographic Profile, Epidemiology, Management and Visual Outcomes of Pediatric Cataract in A Tertiary Eye Care Center of Bangladesh

in Tumkur district of Karnataka shows whole globe anomalies and uveal coloboma to be the main cause of blindness [26]. Lens anomaly was the most common cause of avoidable blindness in the same study [26]. In the present study, among the etiology of cataract, 14.7% cataract cases were idiopathic. Significant cause was maternal TORCH infection present in 39.2% cases, with history of drug exposure like antibiotic, corticosteroid, anti-psychotic drug and abortifacient. Other etiology was history of premature birth 40 (19.6%), metabolic cause 8(3.9%) and birth trauma 24(11.8 %). Z Song et al also reported that in almost half of the cases of pediatric cataract, no cause could be found [6].

In the present study, second eye was operated one week later because it has been seen that rate of complications is higher if operated earlier and moreover, we can manage second eye better by seeing the post-operative behavior of first eye. Implanting the IOL in children is now more widely accepted. Lambert et al in their study reported that primary IOL implantation in cases of unilateral cataract surgery during first six months of life resulted in improvement in visual outcomes but there are higher complications requiring reoperation [27]. We implanted acrylic hydrophobic IOL with primary posterior capsulotomy in all the children after 2 years of age in our study. Positive vitreous pressure was the most common intra-operative complication encountered by us. Positive vitreous pressure could be handled by using higher viscosity visco-elastic material. The most frequent early post-operative complication was posterior capsular opacification 70 (34.3%), iridocyclitis 40(19.6%), post operative striae keratopathy 56(27.5%) and others. Bar-Sela et al. reported PCO development in 38% cases [28] and Vasavada AR et al reported 39.8% of eyes with visual axis opacification [29]. Whereas, Ghodke A et al reported visual axis opacification in 44% cases [15]. Long term follow-up is essential for detection and management of PCO. Secondary glaucoma was seen in 12(5.9 %) eyes. A Studies from Europe have also reported similar findings, with glaucoma ranging from 9.7% to 15.3%, in their studies [30,31]. Pupillary capture occurs more in those children where atropine is used. Low scleral rigidity and hyperactivity of children can also cause this problem. Age at which cataract is operated is very important for final visual outcome. In the present study, 29.4 % eyes get vision between (6/18-6/60). This might be because of delay in cataract surgery, thus leading to amblyopia and because of other surgical related problems. Visual outcome was seen in 62.7% patients, with final visual acuity of 6/6-6/18. Occlusion therapy was mostly performed in children with unilateral cataract. Compliance to patching was found to be major factor affecting the final visual outcome. Children were prescribed minimum 3-4 hours of patching initially for 3 months in cases of severe amblyopia and 1-2 hours of patching in mild to moderate amblyopia. Ghodke A et al in their study reported that 36.2% eyes had best corrected visual acuity better than 6/18 after cataract extraction at the end of 6 months [15]. Casaer et al found that 45.5% of unilateral cataract and 63.7% of bilateral cataract had final best corrected visual acuity of 20/60 and 20/25 or better respectively [32]. On the other hand, Wilson et al reported that 72% eyes had 20/40 or better best corrected visual acuity [BCVA] at the last follow-up and 94% eyes had 20/100 or better visual acuity [33]. Management of pediatric cataract poses an important problem with respect to changing refraction, technical aspects of surgery as well as functional outcome [34]. The timing of surgery is crucial for successful optical restoration and good postoperative outcome, especially in case of children [35]. Strict follow up and adequate rehabilitation are necessary for good results. In order to address blindness due to cataract, counselling of parents with active case finding combined with and clear referral pathways are extremely important [36].

CONCLUSION

The present study concluded that the most common etiology of pediatric cataract is maternal TORCH infection. Others common etiologies are idiopathic, prematurity, birth trauma. Posterior capsular opacity was the most common long-term complication of pediatric cataract. Iridocyclitis, secondary glaucoma, pupillary capture, striate keratitis and retained lens matter were the common early post operative complication. Post operative good visual outcome of most of the cataract children are between 6/6 to 6/18. A thorough understanding of the critical period of the development of vision is extremely crucial to initiate early diagnosis and treatment within the first 3 months of life, which can even be as early as the first 6 weeks from birth. Hence, screening and early treatment for visually significant cataracts is time demanding in the present world with increasing safety and efficacy of pediatric cataract surgery.

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